

SENTENCE AS THE MAIN UNIT OF SYNTAX

Supervisors: **Egamberdiyeva I., Umaraliyeva B.**

Jurabekova Raykhona - a third - year student at the department of Guiding support, intercultural communication and translation studies, Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages
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Abstract: In this paper, the author provided knowledge about sentence structure in English. And you will learn what a sentence structure is and the different sentence structures.

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In fact, sentence structure is one among the most important grammatical components that acts as the foundation of a language.

A sentence is one of the syntactic constructions - a central and crucial one, but not the only one. Therefore, it can be said that a sentence is a syntactic construction. (In the traditional, most common definition of a sentence, it is called not a "syntactic construction" but a "group of words.") Since every syntactic construction is usually a group of words, defining a sentence as a syntactic construction does not lose the information conveyed in the traditional definition. However, defining a sentence as a syntactic construction is more precise: a syntactic construction is a group of words, but not every group of words constitutes a syntactic construction. By characterizing a sentence as a syntactic construction, we have identified the property that unites a sentence with certain other syntactic units and demonstrated the generic affiliation of the sentence. As for specific features, since we are dealing with a meaningful sign unit of language, they must reflect properties associated with the features of the structure, content and use of sentences - three aspects that characterize each meaningful sign unit of language: structure, semantics and pragmatics.

Attention to sentence components arises not simply from heuristic considerations, but has objective grounds related to the nature of the phenomenon being studied: sentences are not given to native speakers in a ready-made form, but are each time "assembled" and "assembled" by them from words, which are given functional and syntactic meanings within the sentence. Since sentences vary in the complexity of their construction, it is important to establish upper and lower limits for sentence segmentation. Within these limits, the researcher will be working with the components of the sentence itself, and not some other unit.

A sentence member, while maintaining its functional syntactic nature throughout the countless number of real sentences (subject as the source or object of an action, predicate as a predicate of the subject, etc.), while being expressed lexically in different ways or due to possible different referential relationships under identical lexemes, relates as a component of each new sentence to ever-new objects, their properties, and conditions of their existence, thereby ensuring that a finite set of linguistic resources reflects the infinite diversity of the objective world and the worlds created by human intellectual activity. At the same time, a quantitatively limited, historically and socially refined inventory of sentence structural formulas, with a characteristic schema of sentence members and their groups, allows each new situation to be represented, both in terms of the set of participants involved and in terms of their mutual relationships, as something typical and therefore familiar in its most general properties. Thus, each sentence dialectically combines the new and the old, the known and the unknown.

A sentence member is a two-sided linguistic sign, possessing both meaning and form. Its meaning is syntactic function, i.e., the substantive relationship in which a given syntactic element exists in relation to another within a certain syntactic sequence of elements. The form of a sentence member is not only the syntactically significant morphological form of the word, but also characteristics associated with the word's belonging to a certain part of speech or word class within a part of speech, the presence/absence of function words, its position relative to another element, intonation indicators of syntactic connection—in short, everything that allows us to identify a word or group of words as the bearer of a specific syntactic-functional meaning. Thus, syntactic form, unlike morphological form, is multicomponent.

Between the extreme limits of articulation—the upper (predicative unit) and the lower (sentence member) - are intermediate levels of articulation, at which syntactic groups with diverse component compositions are distinguished. Coordinating phrases are characterized by the equal rank of each element of the phrase, while subordinate phrases include a certain element as a central element. The most common subordinating syntactic phrases are those with a notional word as the central element, with words directly or indirectly dependent on it.

The system of sentence parts. What elements constitute the system of sentence parts? Their nomenclature is generally accepted and therefore hardly requires justification. These are the subject, predicate, object, adverbial modifier, and attribute. To some extent, this system is correlative with the system of parts

of speech, but only to a certain extent. Complete parallelism between these two systems is not only undesirable from the perspective of the substantive objectives and capabilities of language, but also impossible in principle, if only because the very structural and semantic nature of some parts of speech inherently in their syntactic polyfunctionality. Thus, a noun, as an expression of the meaning of an object, can be a subject, object, adverbial modifier, adverbial modifier, or the nominal part of a predicate.

Traditionally, sentence parts are divided into primary and secondary. While accepting these designations as conventional (so-called secondary members, like primary ones, can belong to the structural minimum of a sentence; an object is relative to the subject), it must be recognized that the traditionally established division reflects an important differential property of sentence members, namely, their participation/non-participation in the formation of the predicative core of a sentence, in expressing the category of predicativity. The practical convenience and advantage of this division lies in its unambiguity: the subject and predicate are always primary, while the rest of the sentence is always secondary.

If we proceed from the role that sentence members play in forming the structural-semantic minimum of a sentence, it turns out that most objects and some adverbial modifiers (depending on the syntagmatic class of the predicate verb) are just as important and necessary as the subject and predicate.

Thus, elements of the same system are organized differently when considered in terms of their different inherent properties.

Apparently, when establishing a system of sentence members, it would be appropriate to base it on the role of the members in sentence formation and the nature of their mutual relationships. In this case, three main groupings of sentence members can be distinguished..

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